

A DESCRIPTION OF THE METHODS USED TO ANALYZE PUBLICATION GUIDELINES

This document provides a detailed description of the data set, the data collection and methods of analysis to analyze publication guidelines, and which are summarized in the paper *Legitimizing medical writing: Self-regulation or regulatory escape?*

1 DATASET

I first collected publication guidelines and contracts that regulate publication practices, which I found in the Opioid and Drug Industry Documents Archives (IDA) and by querying search engines (see Table 4 in Annexe for an overview of the data set). My query to search the IDA was: “‘contract*’ publication’, which displayed 6,549 results on 3 August 2023. Among these results, I selected:

- Templates of contracts (like statements of work, authorship form and disclosure) concerning the production of scientific publications (the most recent were selected), and
- Publication guidelines authored by pharmaceutical companies.

I found one additional document searching on Qwant (a search engine) ‘good publication practices “publication guidelines”’ on 31 July 2023:

- The Novartis publication guideline from January 2018. The document found was saved on Archive.org:
https://web.archive.org/web/20230823145717/https://www.novartis.com/sites/novartis_com/files/novartis-publication-guidelines-posting.pdf

I also found two additional documents searching on Google ‘pharmaceutical company* publication policy* guide*’ on 1st August 2023:

- The Astellas publication guideline from 2017. The document found was saved on Archive.org:
https://web.archive.org/web/20230823145814/https://www.astellas.com/en/system/files/Policy%20on%20Publications%202017-06-19_En.pdf
- The Pfizer white guide from 2023 (I extracted chapter 17, which focuses on publications). The document found was saved on Archive.org:
<https://web.archive.org/web/20230823150022/https://cdn.pfizer.com/pfizercom/White-Guide-Combine-03-01-23.pdf>

I anonymized the authors mentioned in the contracts, agreements or forms: providing names was unnecessary for the analysis.

Limitations of the data-set

The first limitation of this data set is the size of the corpus, resulting from a lack of availability of guidelines (from pharmaceutical companies), and I could only include those that I found online and in the Industry Documents Archive. The same limitation applies to contracts and other agreements between authors, journals, MECCs, or pharmaceutical companies.

In contrast, guidelines from editors and journals are many and I selected the ICMJE and the GPP because they are often referred to (and especially by the pharmaceutical industry in their contracts with MECCs and authors) but many other exist, like COPE. I also selected the ICMJE versions published roughly at the same time as the GPP versions to assess their evolution over time.

Another limitation is the difference in length of the guidelines, and thus the comparison between documents can be difficult. However, the length also indicates if some topics are overlooked, and potentially deferred to other guidelines.

2 METHODS OF ANALYSIS

After an exploration of the documents with computational methods, I used cluster analysis to guide the qualitative data analysis (Elliott, 2018). In addition to adding nuances to the results obtained with computational methods, the qualitative data analysis permitted the identification of definitions (e.g., ‘author’) and their analysis. Below, I summarise the analytical procedures before providing a more detailed description.

Summary of the analytical procedures

- Categorisation of templates of contracts and publication guidelines,
- Use of computational methods to automatically identify the most frequent topics (e.g., authorship) in these documents. Based on this identification, I manually categorised the main topics and found eight categories,
- Manual coding of these documents; the codes were then categorised according to the same eight categories resulting from computational analysis,
- Identification of the main definitions and categorisation according to the eight categories resulting from computational and manual analyses, and
- Analysis of the changes in these definitions over time and according to the type of actors.

2.1 COMPUTATIONAL METHODS FOR CATEGORIZING THE DOCUMENTS

The computational method I used mainly relies on the Quanteda library 3.3.1 in RStudio.

The process started with cleaning and organising the data according to two clustering methods, i.e., hierarchical clustering and classical multidimensional scaling, which are well-described elsewhere (see Chen, 2023; Schweinberger, 2023).

Data cleaning

Data cleaning consisted of the removal of punctuation, numbers, URLs, symbols, separators (Unicode ‘Separator’ [Z] and ‘Control’ [C] categories), English stop words, and words considered as noise (e.g., the text on the foot page of the documents). I then tokenised the documents into bigrams and trigrams and set the minimum term frequency at 25, and thus kept the most frequent bigrams and trigrams.

Categories of documents

I compared documents based on the frequency of the bigrams and trigrams. Given their length differences, I normalised this Document-Feature Matrices (DFM1) with `dfm_weight(dfm, scheme="prop")`. I then applied `textstat_dist()` on DFM1 to calculate the “Canberra” distance between documents and clustered the documents with `hclust()` for the following visualisation:

Figure 1 Distance among documents belonging to the corpus

This dendrogram helps visualising the proximity of documents. I then explored the content.

2.2 COMPUTATIONAL METHODS FOR IDENTIFYING THE MAIN TOPICS IN THE DOCUMENTS

I created a second DFM (DFM2) encompassing all sentences of all documents, irrespective of the guidelines to which they belong. I then tokenized them (bigrams and trigrams, with a minimum frequency of 25). In the DFM2, rows are sentences and columns are bigrams and trigrams. Cells represent the total number of times the bigrams and trigrams appear in each sentence.

I first used `textstat_frequency()` from the `Quanteda` library (3.3.1) to explore the frequency of bigrams and trigrams in the corpus:

Figure 2 Frequency of bigrams and trigrams in the corpus

Using DFM1, I also generated a visualisation of the frequency of bigrams for each document to control whether one or several documents are skewing the results given that their length differs. I thus performed `textstat_frequency()` on each document:

Figure 3 Frequency of bigrams and trigrams for each document (scales vary)

In Figure 3, scales vary according to the length of the documents. It shows the importance of a few key bigrams or trigrams for each document. It already shows a few prominent topics in some of them. For example, ‘clinical trial’ seems to appear frequently in top positions in several documents.

For an overview of the connections between bigrams and trigrams, I visualised the number of times bigrams and trigrams appear together within sentences (DFM2):

Figure 4 Network based on the distance of the bigrams per sentence in the corpus

As Figure 4 suggests, ‘clinical trial’ is one of the most frequent bigrams and is quite central in the network. Both Figure 3 and Figure 4 can complement each other to enrich the meaning of the frequency of bigrams and trigrams. However, it raises more questions than it provides answers. For example, ‘clinical trial’ seems to often appear in connection with ‘steering committee’, which requires more context to understand this connection. I thus further explored the data set

to find categories that could provide more context to these words, using hierarchical clustering and classical multidimensional scaling, as described below.

Distances

Quanteda allows either positional analysis, which corresponds to string-of-words (with `textstat_*` or `textmodel_*`) or non-positional analysis, which corresponds to bag-of-words, based on the calculation of frequencies of features in a document (within a DFM) (see Benoit et al., 2018).

FCM (feature co-occurrence matrix in a defined context)

For word clustering, it is first key to estimate ‘pairwise word similarities, based on their tendency to co-occur in similar contexts’ (Momtazi et al., 2010). I thus needed an FCM, which consists of a count of the co-occurrence of features (bigram and trigram in this case) within a defined context. This context can be documents, sentences within documents, syntactic relationships between features (nouns within a sentence, for instance), or a window (2010). When the context is a window, a weighting function is typically applied, that is, a function that calculates the distance from the target word (see Jurafsky & Martin, 2023), and the ordered co-occurrence of the two features (bigrams or trigrams) is considered (Church & Hanks, 1990). In the FCM produced for this study, the context is sentences, regardless of the document where they appear, and columns and rows are bigrams or trigrams.

Distance matrix computation

`dist()` computes the distance between rows of the matrix to produce a distance matrix from an FCM. Different measures of distance exist, and I used the default one: Euclidean. After applying `dist()` to the FCM, hierarchical clustering can be performed (e.g., Schweinberger, 2023).

Hierarchical Clustering

I used `hclust()` for hierarchical clustering, even though it bears a strong limitation: the lack of statistical tests. An alternative exists, `pvclust()`, which provides Approximately Unbiased p-values and Bootstrap Probability value (Desagulier, 2022; Pvclust, 2017/2023). However, I could not use `pvclust()`, as it does not take a `dist()` object.

I thus used `hclust()` (with the ‘ward2’ method) and visualised the clusters of the corpus with a dendrogram, which is more readable than plots (see Desagulier, 2017). I also manually configured the plot to distinguish 16 categories (by colours) in the dendrogram with the library `ape` version 5.7-1.:

Figure 5 Hierarchical clustering

The concepts in the main categories are the most frequent co-occurring bigrams in all the documents. The dendrogram also indicates a hierarchization of the co-occurrence of these bigrams. Although the hierarchical cluster analysis highlights the most important co-occurring bigrams, their hierarchies poorly represent the meaning of the texts.

Given the limitations of `hclust()`, I wanted to compare the results of hierarchical clustering and of classical multidimensional scaling (MDS) and thus applied MDS to visualise the clusters of bigrams and trigrams in the FCM.

Classical multidimensional scaling

I first used `cmdscale()` to apply MDS to the distance matrix (see Distance matrix computation above). MDS requires the `k`-means to be set manually, and I selected 10. Results can be compared with those provided by `hclust()` above. For clarity purposes, I provide the results without and with labels (respectively, Figure 6 and Figure 7).

Figure 6 Classical multidimensional scaling (without labels)

Figure 7 Classical multidimensional scaling (with labels)

Results from `cmdscale()` are different from hierarchical clustering. Even though it can be difficult to read, it highlights three outliers, ‘clinical trial’, ‘steering committee’, and ‘secondary publication’. The rest is much less readable than Figure 5. It indicates a close proximity of the bigrams and trigrams within sentences. In other words, it suggests that the most frequent bigrams and trigrams seem to often co-occur in sentences across the corpus.

Although these categories offer a visualisation of the proximity of bigrams and trigrams, they only offer general guidance to analyse the topics of these texts. Manual coding of these documents was indeed necessary to do a more fine-grained analysis.

2.3 QUALITATIVE METHODS

Manual coding was used to complement and address the limitations of computational methods. I used qualitative data analysis methods, based on the results from computational analysis.

A summary of the qualitative methods:

- The reading of all publication guidelines,
- The automatic separation of each sentence of the documents in an Excel file (with 'tokenize_sentences' from tokenizers 0.3.0),
- The manual coding of every sentence (often with the main keyword of the title or of the paragraph) to categorize them by topic. The sentences that concerned the writing of the guidelines (e.g., authors, 'about' section, acknowledgements for the guidelines, titles, etc.), tables of content and bibliographies were left out. I coded a total of 3710 sentences, as summarized in Table 1,
- The identification of all definitions in the documents, and
- The comparison of the evolution of definitions and topics over time.

Table 1 Summary of the codes per document

<i>Documents</i>	<i>#sentences</i>	<i>%Sentences</i>	<i>#Codes</i>	<i>%Codes</i>
<i>2004_ICMJE_Reco</i>	701	14.2	484	13.0
<i>2008_ICMJE_RecoCoding</i>	840	17.1	517	13.9
<i>2015_ICMJE_Reco</i>	653	13.3	513	13.8
<i>2023_ICMJE_RecoRev</i>	787	16.0	627	16.9
<i>Astellas_Policy_Publication_2017</i>	15	0.3	14	0.4
<i>GPP_2003Rev</i>	138	2.8	124	3.3
<i>GPP_2022_SupplementRev</i>	505	10.3	448	12.1
<i>GPP2_2009Rev</i>	142	2.9	129	3.5
<i>GPP2022UpdateRev</i>	205	4.2	146	3.9
<i>GPP3_2015Rev</i>	343	7.0	214	5.8
<i>gqff0240_MNKSOW_Cactus_2014_OCR</i>	27	0.5	18	0.5
<i>gsxv0238_MNKSOW_Medlogix_2013_OCR</i>	25	0.5	17	0.5
<i>jhnv0238_2016_AuthorshipDisclosure_MNK</i>	36	0.7	20	0.5
<i>kylp0237_MNKSOW_CHC_2014_OCR</i>	46	0.9	39	1.1
<i>novartis_publication_guidelines_2018</i>	64	1.3	63	1.7
<i>nsmn0273_INSYSSOW_Synchrony_2013_OCR</i>	18	0.4	15	0.4
<i>ID_Rev</i>				
<i>Pfizer_WhitePaper_Publication_2023</i>	76	1.5	74	2.0
<i>pzif0226_2009_TakedaPubGuid</i>	77	1.6	72	1.9
<i>qqdj0253_2016_MallinckrodtPubGuid</i>	136	2.8	111	3.0
<i>rhbj0236_MNKAuthorAgreement_2012_OCR</i>	37	0.8	30	0.8
<i>yskl0237_JournalOpioidManagement_Author_2012</i>	32	0.6	18	0.5
<i>zgf0235_AmJournalManagedCare_Author_2015</i>	22	0.4	17	0.5
Total	4925	100	3710	100

To build categories, I compared different codes across guidelines to harmonize them (e.g., 'competing manuscript' is called differently according to the documents). After coding the sentences, I reviewed and adjusted the codes twice according to the topics found with the cluster analysis previously performed.

Main categories

- *Relationships between actors*: this category refers to any definitional elements of a relation between actors, for example ‘relationship activities’, ‘potential conflicts’, ‘conflict of interest’.
- *Type of actors*: this category concerns all the actors mentioned in the guidelines. In the results of the hierarchical clustering method, many are cited, like ‘publication professional’ or ‘professional writer’.
- *Type of scientific communications*: this category refers to all the different types of publication and scientific communication mentioned in the guidelines, like primary and secondary publications.
- *Content of publication*: this category concerns the structure or the content of scientific communications, like ‘title page’.
- *Norms*: this category encompasses all normative elements that participate in defining, explaining, and recommending how an actor should behave. It can thus be binding norms (like ‘trial registration’), or softer norms (like ‘reporting guideline’).
- *Data*: this category concerns all elements that refer to data, like ‘study data’. It often refers to sharing data or data access.
- *Steps of the research process*: this category includes mostly traditional steps of the research process like clinical trials, but also usual steps implemented by the medical writing industry, like ‘publication development’ or ‘publication process’.
- *Principles*: this category refers to any concept governing these guidelines (e.g., ‘editorial freedom’) that is not a norm.

Table 2 Overview of the codes by category and type of industry (heatmap)

	Scientific publishing	Medical writers	Pharmaceutical companies	Total
Total	2041	862	453	3356
Categories				
<i>Type of scientific communications</i>	353	178	79	610
%Type of scientific communications	17.3	20.6	17.4	
<i>Type of actor</i>	240	267	113	620
%Type of actor	11.8	31.0	13.1	
<i>Relationships between actors</i>	214	91	94	399
%Relationships between actors	10.5	4.5	10.9	
<i>Norms</i>	176	101	61	338
%Norms	8.6	11.7	13.5	
<i>Steps of the research process</i>	209	121	50	380

%Steps of the research process	10.2	14.0	11.0	
<i>Data</i>	13	27	23	63
%Data	0.6	3.1	5.1	
<i>Content of publication</i>	531	8	17	556
%Content of publication	26.0	0.9	3.8	
<i>Principles</i>	305	69	16	390
%Principles	14.9	8.0	3.5	

Percentages are calculated based on the documents that are classified according to their authors, like ‘scientific publishing’ (columns). For example, the category ‘type of actor’ is overrepresented in the ‘medical writers’ category. Also, the category ‘content of publication’ represents more than a quarter of scientific publishing’s coded sentences.

I also coded references to other norms (see Table 3). If a reference refers to another guideline, it is either to complement the current guidelines, to change it slightly, or to copy something from that other document. For example, the concept of authorship defined by the ICMJE is often referred to, and its definition is either adopted or modified. In this category, I thus distinguished external and internal policies:

- External policies refer to those that are foreign to the institution, and
- Internal policies correspond to those that were produced by the institution that authored the guidelines.

Table 3 References used per type of actors (heatmap)

References	Use	Scientific publishing	Medical writers	Pharmaceutical companies
agreement	96	14	34	38
ICMJE	86	13	44	39
external policies	60	30	25	5
journals' policies	58	41	13	4
internal policies	47	26	10	2
copyright	38	8	17	22

Table 3 is an extract of the table of the most cited references by document. I selected here the references used more than 30 times within the corpus.

Figure 9 Number of definitions by date and by category

I also compared definitions according to the categories they belong to and according to the type of actors who wrote them:

Figure 10 Number of definitions by category and by industry

This quantitative overview of categories and definitions provides a sense of their distribution by date and by type of industry.

Finally, I coded definitions when they first appeared in the corpus, when they were split, adopted, when an alternative definition was created, when two definitions were merged and when an existing definition was redefined. The result can be visualized below:

3 BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Benoit, K., Watanabe, K., Wang, H., Nulty, P., Obeng, A., Müller, S., & Matsuo, A. (2018).
quanteda: An R package for the quantitative analysis of textual data. *Journal of Open
Source Software*, 3(30), 774. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.00774>
- Chen, A. C.-H. (2023). *Chapter 12 Vector Space Representation in Corpus Linguistics*.
Department of English, NTNU.
[https://alvinnntnu.github.io/NTNU_ENC2036_LECTURES/vector-space-
representation.html](https://alvinnntnu.github.io/NTNU_ENC2036_LECTURES/vector-space-representation.html)
- Church, K. W., & Hanks, P. (1990). Word Association Norms, Mutual Information, and
Lexicography. *Computational Linguistics*, 16(1), 22–29.
- Desagulier, G. (2017, November 27). Clustering corpus data with multidimensional scaling
[Billet]. *Around the word*. <https://corpling.hypotheses.org/3497>
- Desagulier, G. (2022, July 4). Validating clusters in hierarchical cluster analysis [Billet]. *Around
the word*. <https://corpling.hypotheses.org/2675>
- Elliott, V. (2018). Thinking about the Coding Process in Qualitative Data Analysis. *The Qualitative
Report*. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2018.3560>
- Jurafsky, D., & Martin, J. H. (2023). Automatic Speech Recognition and Text-to-Speech. In
Speech and Language Processing: Vol. 3rd edition draft.
<https://web.stanford.edu/~jurafsky/slp3/>
- Momtazi, S., Khudanpur, S., & Klakow, D. (2010). A Comparative Study of Word Co-occurrence
for Term Clustering in Language Model-based Sentence Retrieval. In R. Kaplan, J.
Burstein, M. Harper, & G. Penn (Eds.), *Human Language Technologies: The 2010 Annual
Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational
Linguistics* (pp. 325–328). Association for Computational Linguistics.
<https://aclanthology.org/N10-1046>

Pvclust. (2023). [R]. Shimodaira Laboratory. <https://github.com/shimo-lab/pvclust> (Original work published 2017)

Schweinberger, M. (2023). *Language Technology and Data Analysis Laboratory (LADAL)*. The University of Queensland, School of Languages and Cultures.
<https://slcladal.github.io/index.html>

4 LISTS OF FIGURES AND TABLES

Figures

Figure 1 Distance among documents belonging to the corpus.....	3
Figure 2 Frequency of bigrams and trigrams in the corpus.....	3
Figure 3 Frequency of bigrams and trigrams for each document (scales vary)	4
Figure 4 Network based on the distance of the bigrams per sentence in the corpus	4
Figure 5 Hierarchical clustering.....	6
Figure 6 Classical multidimensional scaling (without labels).....	7
Figure 7 Classical multidimensional scaling (with labels).....	7
Figure 8 Number of codes by date and by category	11
Figure 9 Number of definitions by date and by category.....	12
Figure 10 Number of definitions by category and by industry	12

Tables

Table 1 Summary of the codes per document	8
Table 2 Overview of the codes by category and type of industry (heatmap).....	9
Table 3 References used per type of actors (heatmap)	10
Table 4 The data set.....	17

5 ANNEXES

Table 4 The data set

Source/ID	Date	Document name	Type of industry	Document Author(s)	Sub-contractor	#Words ¹
<i>CURRENT MEDICAL RESEARCH AND OPINION</i>	2003	GPP	Medical writing industry	--	--	1784
<i>BMJ Research Methods & Reporting</i>	2009	GPP2	Medical writing industry	--	--	2601
<i>Annals of Internal Medicine RESEARCH AND REPORTING METHODS</i>	2015	GPP3	Medical writing industry	--	--	4500
<i>Annals of Internal Medicine RESEARCH AND REPORTING METHODS</i>	2022	GPP & supplement (two documents)	Medical writing industry	--	--	2068 + 6207
<i>ICMJE website</i>	2004	ICMJE	Scientific publishing industry	Editors	--	6571
<i>ICMJE website</i>	2008	ICMJE	Scientific publishing industry	Editors	--	6953
<i>ICMJE website</i>	2015	ICMJE	Scientific publishing industry	Editors	--	7329
<i>ICMJE website</i>	2023	ICMJE	Scientific publishing industry	Editors	--	8418
<i>Qwant</i>	2018	Publication guidelines	Pharmaceutical industry	Novartis	--	1010
<i>Google</i>	2023	Publication guidelines	Pharmaceutical industry	Pfizer	--	1408
<i>IDA (pzjf0226)</i>	2009	Publication guidelines	Pharmaceutical industry	Takeda	--	1577
<i>IDA (qqdj0253)</i>	2016	Publication guidelines	Pharmaceutical industry	Mallinckrodt	--	1747
<i>Google</i>	2017	Publication guidelines	Pharmaceutical industry	Astellas	--	144
<i>IDA (jhnv0238)</i>	2016	Authorship disclosure	Pharmaceutical industry	Mallinckrodt	Author	360
<i>IDA (gqff0240)</i>	2014	Contract	Pharmaceutical industry	Mallinckrodt	Cactus	275
<i>IDA (gsxv0238)</i>	2013	Contract	Pharmaceutical industry	Mallinckrodt	MedLogix	512
<i>IDA (kylp0237)</i>	2014	Contract	Pharmaceutical industry	Mallinckrodt	CHC	666
<i>IDA (nsmn0273)</i>	2013	Contract	Pharmaceutical industry	Insys	Synchrony	423
<i>IDA (rhhj0236)</i>	2012	Contract	Pharmaceutical industry	Synchrony	Author	754
<i>IDA (zgfh0235)</i>	2015	Authorship Form	Scientific publishing industry	The American Journal of Managed Care	Author	331
<i>IDA (yskl0237)</i>	2012	Publication Agreement	Scientific publishing industry	Journal of Opioid Management	Authors	367

¹ Approximate number of words after cleaning the documents with RStudio, these figures only provide an order of magnitude of their length.